

Quantum Resolution Entropy? Part III

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In Part II, we argued that the free particle quantum wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ is really a self-measurement function which manifests itself physically. In other words, a constant p and $pp/2m$ at each x (classical notions) requires a periodic function in x and p to provide self-measurement.

In this note, we ask two questions. First, what exactly is being measured and secondly, why does one really need self-measurement when Newtonian mechanics is based on external nondisturbing measurements?

Newtonian Measurements

Physics requires measurement. Newtonian mechanics relies on nondisturbing external measurement, e.g..bouncing photons off particles for example. A particle with momentum p moving through space, however, does not require a measurement in order to justify its state, If one classically measures its impulse against a target at some x,t , one may say that at earlier x,t values it also had x and p if it was moving through a vacuum.

In Part II, we argued that a quantum free particle wavefunction $\exp(i p \cdot r)$ represents a self-measurement function which has physical consequences. This function, however, is associated with a very particular measurement, namely one associated with momentum, i.e. impulse hits. Secondly, it is not clear why one must have a self-measurement mechanism.

Quantum Free Particle

A quantum free particle moves through space with some velocity and has a momentum p and kinetic $pp/2m$ nonrelativistically. If it strikes a target, it may render an impulse proportional to p . In this respect, it seems to be completely classical and it is not clear why self-measurement is required, especially as manifested in space.

The requirement of self-measurement seems to emerge, as we have argued in previous notes, in examples for which total energy remains constant while p changes suddenly at a point, i.e. at a $V1$ constant- $V2$ constant potential interface for particles. (For a photon, this is equivalent to one dimensional reflection-refraction.) Classically the particle may reflect or it may move into the $V2$ region with a changed p . Experimentally, the probability is not .5 for each of these, which means that there must be an underlying explanation for the probability to reflect and that to refract (change p and move forward). No microscopic description, however, is given of the potentials $V1$ and $V2$. They only represent different energies. Certainly impulses based on p occur in this problem and space is a factor because there is a point interface. This point, however, may be moved as there is translational invariance. As a result, one might postulate a kind of information function based on p,x i.e. $f(p,x)$ which may be associated with continuity at the junction and also linked with translational invariance. This information function, however, is equivalent to a self-measurement, otherwise how is the information obtained?

Given that the particle may reflect or refract, a steady stream picture so at the transition point one has equal information for the LHS and RHS i.e.

$$Af(x_a, p) + Bf(x_a, -p) = Cf(x_a, p^2) \quad ((1))$$

Here we assume that the information function adds linearly. A is weight for the incident particle, B the reflected and C the refracted. One may arbitrarily set A to 1, but there are still two unknowns B, C and $f(x_a, p)$ is completely unknown as well.

((1)) should hold for $x_a \rightarrow x_a + d$ where d is tiny due to translational invariance, so:

$$((1)) \text{ and } d A \frac{df}{dx}(p) + d B \frac{df}{dx}(-p) = C d \frac{df}{dx}(p^2) \text{ at } x_a \quad ((2))$$

One now has two equations with two unknowns B, C and the unknown f. Translational invariance was used to obtain the set ((1)), ((2)), but it seems that these might be combined to eliminate x_a by eliminating f. If f is a self-measurement or information function, then the only information it carries is p, so one might expect df/dx to be proportional to p. This would allow the combination of ((1)) and ((2)) to possibly create a pressure balance equation with no $f(x, p)$ present. This occurs if:

$$f(x, p) = \exp(ipx) \quad ((3))$$

((3)) is complex, but it is an information function so there is no immediate issue. This suggests that even a free particle in space is associated with $\exp(ipx)$ which, in turn, is directly linked to p. In other words, one no longer has only the classical notion of a p impulse but also the notion of a periodic function in x (two dimensional). This result emerges solely through self-measurement arguments which are required to balance probabilistic p information for an incident/reflected particle with a transmitted/refracted one. At the transition point there is an equivalence in information/measurement and there needs to be a special function, linked with translational invariance i.e. the generator d/dx , to account for this information. It is not enough to simply argue that p values change if there is reflection and refraction, as one would do classically. This sheds no light on the experimentally observable probabilities to reflect or transmit. As a result, there is more to impulse than simply an impulse hit.

We suggest that classical momentum is associated with an information function $\exp(ipx)$ which has physical consequences in that there is an associated spatial probability (and hence resolution entropy). This associated spatial probability is required to account for probabilistic p changes, as in the case of reflection/refraction. Self-measurement of p must be maintained because there is some kind of p related information equivalency at the transition point in space. The fact that $\exp(ipx)$ is probabilistic (and hence linked with resolution entropy) is tied to the fact that probabilistic changes may occur in momentum. Thus, one has the deterministic value of p (proportional to a deterministic impulse hit), but there is also the associated probabilistic spatial probability/entropy which handles probabilistic changes in space. As a result, it is not enough to describe a particle with momentum p (and a velocity v) by only these variables, we argue.

Thus a self-measurement, even in free space, is probabilistic in nature.

Single Particle Quantum Bound State

As a final note, we consider classical deterministic bound state behaviour. Such behaviour yields kinetic energy as a function of x as overall energy is constant, i.e. $KE + V(x)$. Quantum mechanically, the “average” kinetic energy is the same as the classical one. In other words, kinetic energy is thought of in the same way in quantum mechanics, it is just that there is an associated information function, the wavefunction, which is probabilistic in x . This is real and usually periodic with differing peak heights and widths. $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W / W$ again gives the kinetic energy based on this information function, but one sees that the dynamics (i.e. motion) is linked with a spatial probability distribution, which in turn represents resolution entropy. W is again a self-measurement function, but unlike $\exp(ipx)$, $W^*(x)W(x)$ represents a physical distribution in space (which is measurable) while $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)=1$, i.e. no preferred x point. This does not mean that there are not x probability fluctuations as p moves through space. These are described by the two dimensional dynamic probability and are physically real as they are “picked up” by a two slit apparatus with slit separation of the order of \hbar/p .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we ask why a particle with momentum p should have an associated probability or self-measurement function $\exp(ipx)$ (called a wavefunction). Why should it not simply be enough that such a particle imparts an impulse proportional to p upon collision with a target? What a priori reason is there for a self-measurement, and a probabilistic one at that, in space? We argue that knowing p is not enough based on experimental grounds. In nature, there exists a probabilistic one dimensional reflection-refraction problem, even for particles with rest mass (i.e. a V_1 constant - V_2 constant interface at x). Simply stating that there is a probability to have a reflected particle with $-p$ and another probability to have a transmitted one with p_2 is not providing enough information. The probabilities do not seem to follow from the nature of V_1, V_2 which is unknown microscopically. As a result, one may postulate that extra information is associated with p , namely spatial information which allows for an equivalency to be established at the transition point. This suggests an information or self-measurement function $f(x,p)$. We suggest that this information adds linearly, i.e. $Af(xa,p) + Bf(xa,-p) = Cf(xa,p_2)$, where A is an incident weight, B a reflected and C a refracted. If one imposes translational invariance, one may write $x_a \rightarrow x_a + d$, where d is tiny. This leads to two equations, i.e. a second in df/dx . If one suggests that the two equations should yield momentum balance and remove x_a dependence explicitly, one has a solution of $f(x,p) = \exp(ipx)$.

This, we argue, is the self-measurement probability which manifests itself physically. One does not simply have momentum p (and a velocity) which imparts an impulse. There is also this experimentally required probability (resolution entropy) accompanying p which allows one to handle probabilistic changes in p using information ideas.